

FEMCE – A 3D finite element simulation tool for magnetic refrigerants

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ABSTRACT

A critical challenge for magnetic refrigeration is designing shape-optimized refrigerants. When applying a magnetic field to the refrigerant, its magnetocaloric effect (MCE) heterogeneity is directly related to the demagnetizing field (a geometric phenomenon). Striking a balance between the total mass/volume of refrigerant, and its effective performance at a given temperature and applied magnetic field is a complex non-linear magnetostatics problem. We present a tool for estimating both the spatially-resolved and effective MCE for any refrigerant design, via the 3D finite element method - Finite Element Magnetocaloric Effect (FEMCE). FEMCE allows the user to input complex refrigerant shapes, together with the thermophysical properties of the material, to estimate and optimize its refrigerant performance for a given temperature and applied magnetic field change. The tool can be readily employed for both the conventional and demagnetizing-field induced MCE.

1. Introduction

Magnetic refrigeration, the act of cooling using solid state magnetic materials (refrigerants) through the magnetocaloric effect (MCE), is an alternative to vapor-compression refrigeration (Klinar et al., 2024, Franco et al., 2018, Gschneidner and Pecharsky, 2008). Cooling efficiency is a key aspect for refrigerators, and in magnetic refrigeration the shape and composition of the refrigerant will dictate its performance (Badosa et al., 2023, Lipsø et al., 2011).

For any magnetic field source (permanent magnets or otherwise), the useful available volume for the refrigerant is a constraint (Franco et al., 2018). With a limited volume of magnetic refrigerant, designing its optimal shape and layout is crucial for the optimization of magnetic refrigerators (Lipsø et al., 2011, Smith et al., 2012).

The internal magnetic field is generally non-uniform so the refrigerant will exhibit a heterogeneous temperature change correlated to its shape (Lipsø et al., 2011, Bahl and Nielsen, 2009) - the demagnetizing field (H_d). The impact of the demagnetizing field on the temperature change of refrigerants is experimentally observable through thermography (Christensen et al., 2010, Pereira et al., 2023) and thermocouples (Lipsø et al., 2011). This demagnetizing field reduces the total available cooling power of the refrigerant as the MCE will be less intense in regions where the H_d is strongest, decreasing the effective MCE of the refrigerant.

To evaluate the optimal mass/volume refrigerant configuration, multiple numerical models have been developed (Mugica et al., 2018,

Plait et al., 2018, Bouchard et al., 2009), but are not targeted at complex 3D geometries. In addition to in-house numerical models, there are commercial general use multiphysics software for the simulation of magnetic refrigerants, but by being task-agnostic they are inherently more difficult to use than purpose-built software. The input thermomagnetic properties of the refrigerant, namely magnetization ($M(H,T)$) and specific heat ($C_p(H,T)$), are temperature (T) and magnetic field (H) dependent. Taking these dependencies under consideration in a general-use multiphysics software is not facilitated.

2. FEMCE

To allow the geometric optimization of 3D magnetic refrigerants with direct input of their temperature and magnetic field dependent thermomagnetic properties, a simulation software is here presented - Finite Element Magnetocaloric Effect (FEMCE), available at <https://github.com/rkiefe/femce>.

FEMCE operates exclusively through its user interface, displayed in Fig. 1, for ease of use. A simulation can be executed entirely from FEMCE, including: drawing the refrigerant model with cuboid shapes; create the finite element mesh; simulate the MCE (adiabatic temperature change and isothermal heat exchange), along with other relevant properties such as the spatially resolved magnetic field.

The 3D object maker in FEMCE is simplistic (only cuboids), but more complex refrigerant shapes can be created with external tools (via CAD software) and then imported to FEMCE by conventional .stl files.

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Fig. 1. FEMCE interface with the element-wise ΔT for a refrigerant example.

To simulate the interaction between the refrigerant and the external magnetic field, the user must provide magnetization ($M(H, T)$) data of the refrigerant. In addition, to estimate the heterogeneous temperature change, the user must also provide the specific heat ($C_p(H, T)$). With both thermomagnetic properties, the MCE, which consists in the temperature and entropy change from applying or removing a magnetic field, is determined by the following standard equations (Smith et al., 2012, Amaral and Amaral, 2010),

$$dT = -\frac{T}{C_p} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial T} \right)_H dH \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta S = \int_0^H \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial T} \right)_H dH \quad (2)$$

As an approximation, specific heat (C_p) can be provided as solely temperature dependent or as a constant. Alternatively, the user can provide $\Delta T(H, T)$ data directly, in which case C_p data is not required.

The Finite Element Method (FEM) is implemented to calculate the internal magnetic field H of the magnetic refrigerant design, which is then used to evaluate ΔT , ΔS and its associated heat exchange, from Eqs. (1) and (2). These quantities are evaluated element-wise, but FEMCE also outputs their scalar volume averages. These averages can be convenient for a quick evaluation of the performance of a given refrigerant design.

While FEMCE is targeted at evaluating the MCE, the user can input only $M(H, T)$ and simulate the internal magnetic field of the refrigerant, at the desired temperature. In turn, FEMCE will output the internal magnetic field (\vec{H}) and magnetization (\vec{M}) of each mesh element and their overall average values, as well as an effective scalar demagnetizing factor of the refrigerant at its orientation in respect to the applied field.

3. Model and numerical approach

With complex refrigerant geometries, the spatially resolved internal magnetic field is required to evaluate the MCE, which can be obtained by the following magnetostatics formulation (Kuczmann and Iványi, 2008):

$$\begin{aligned} -\vec{\nabla} \cdot (\mu(r, H) \vec{\nabla} u) &= 0 \\ -\vec{\nabla} u \cdot \vec{n} |_{\Gamma_{\text{ext}}} &= \vec{H}_{\text{applied}} \cdot \vec{n} \\ -\vec{\nabla} u &= \vec{H}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

a non-linear Poisson equation with Neumann boundary conditions where u is the magnetic scalar potential. This formulation assumes the absence of electric currents, and uses the definition $\chi = M/H$ (magnetic susceptibility (Coey, 2010)), and the magnetic permeability μ defined

as $\mu = \mu_0(1 + \chi)$. This is a non-linear differential equation as $\chi = \chi(u)$. An iterative approach is employed to handle this non-linearity (Larson and Bengzon, 2015):

$$\chi^{(n)} = (1 - \epsilon) \chi^{(n-1)} + \epsilon \frac{M^{(n)}}{H^{(n)}}$$

where $\epsilon \leq 1$ and is adjustable by the user in FEMCE's interface at the "advanced settings" tab, under the "iteration weight" field. A smaller value slows the convergence speed, but better guarantees that it converges.

FEM consists in subdividing the domain volume into finite elements, in this case tetrahedrons, and approximating the solution by unknown coefficients (u_i) and a known basis function ($\phi(x, y, z)$): $u = \sum_i u_i \phi_i$, turning the differential Eq. (3) into a matrix equation. This approach is inherently compatible with complex geometries (not ellipsoidal, cuboid or cylindrical), and is a standard numerical approach for solving differential equations with arbitrarily shaped domains (Kuczmann and Iványi, 2008, Chen, 2005).

To create the tetrahedron mesh, the built-in mesh generator from MATLAB is used. By default, mesh generation parameters are automatically set, but depending on the geometry and accuracy desired, manual input of target maximum and/or minimum element sizes may be provided. Additionally, users can set a by-edge local refinement target which bypasses the minimum and maximum element size for each edge requested by the user in the edge list. Local refinement together with strategic maximum and minimum element sizing increases simulation resolution with efficient computational cost.

Simulating the magnetic field solely on the magnetic region (exclusively through FEM) is not sufficient, thanks to the well known open boundary problem (Chantrell et al., 2001). So, a box container is created, simulating the refrigerant and the space around it. This surrounding box is automatically generated for the input .stl, 5 times larger than the refrigerant model, as typically employed (Chen and Konrad, 1997).

The solution u is determined only up to a constant. This degree of freedom can be resolved by an additional constraint through the Lagrange multiplier technique (Larson and Bengzon, 2015), implemented in FEMCE. After obtaining the scalar potential u , the magnetic field H is easily found for each element of the mesh by its definition $\vec{H} = -\vec{\nabla} u$. As a result, Eqs. (1) and (2) can be implemented on each element of the mesh, obtaining an element-wise ΔT and ΔS .

3.1. Validation of implementation

A standard approach to validate a finite element implementation is to compare the numerical result to a known analytical solution (Reddy, 2005). The solution to the non-linear Poisson equation (eq. (3)) with Neumann boundary conditions is not uniquely defined. We consider a possible analytic solution to the Poisson equation $u = \cos(x+y+z)$ and $\mu = \frac{C}{\sqrt{1-u^2}}$, where u is a solution to the differential equation, considering a non-linear term $\mu(u)$. The x , y and z are the spatial coordinates and C is an arbitrary constant, fixed by a boundary condition, which is set such that the function u is a solution.

In Fig. 2, the average relative difference between the analytic and numerical solution is displayed, considering an increasingly refined mesh (more elements). The accuracy of the numerical solution is stable, showing a quickly converging average error with mesh refinement. Once the method converges, a higher element count provides essentially a higher spatial resolution rather than an increase in numerical accuracy.

Using the approach mentioned above, the numerical solution to u achieves an average error smaller than 0.8% using 16 thousand elements, taking 58 s to compute on a 2.2 GHz Intel i7-8750H CPU, in a single-threaded execution. If the differential equation is linear (μ is independent of u), this approach has a maximum error within double

Fig. 2. Relative difference (%) between the numerical result of eq. 3 with FEM and its analytic solution, according to the number of elements in the mesh.

precision accuracy.

An alternative validation method was also tested, by considering the analytic result of a magnetizable sphere under a uniform external field. The sphere exhibits a uniform magnetization and internal magnetic field, with a known analytic solution for its magnetization (Bruckner et al., 2012):

$$M = \frac{3\chi}{3 + \chi} H_{app},$$

where χ is the linear magnetic susceptibility of the sphere and H_{app} is the external applied field. Independent of the value of χ , the relationship between the sphere’s magnetization and the applied field hold. A range of χ values between 1.5 and 10^5 (dimensionless) were tested.

Considering a mesh with 5 thousand elements in the magnetic domain (21 thousand in total), the average relative difference of the expected magnetization and our numerical result is 0.4%, comparable to other FEM implementations in magnetostatics (Bruckner et al., 2012), taking around 3 ss to compute.

4. Example: standard refrigerant designs

As a use case example of FEMCE, we consider a conventional magnetic refrigerant layout which consists in a stack of rectangular sheets of gadolinium (Gd) evenly spaced (Yu et al., 2010). A common process of inducing the temperature change in this scenario is by placing the refrigerant inside an Halbach magnet. FEMCE evaluates the performance of this refrigerant layout and allows a more in-depth analysis of the cooling power available and the ΔT heterogeneity. The refrigerant was designed using CAD software and then its geometry was imported to FEMCE through an .stl file. The input thermomagnetic properties of Gd required for simulation of this refrigerant can be obtained either from experimental data or simulated. In this example, we used mean field theory (MFT), which reasonably replicates the relevant properties of Gd (Bahl and Nielsen, 2009). We run this simulation at a temperature of 293 K, where ΔT is around 4.2 K for a 1 T magnetic field change.

Considering a useful cylindrical volume of an Halbach magnet, 8 sheets of Gd with their outer perimeter conforming to a cylinder are created. Each sheet of 0.5 mm thickness is spaced by 1 mm, the width of each sheet being 14.4, 16.2, 17.3 and 17.7 mm respectively.

Using a mesh with 62 thousand elements, the heterogeneous ΔT of this refrigerant is shown in Fig. 3. The applied field (1.0 T) is parallel to the surface of the Gd sheets, along the short axis.

This layout exhibits an effective temperature change of 4.0 K, lower than the nominal 4.2 K of the MFT dataset. This decrease in ΔT is a direct result of the demagnetizing field of the refrigerant, which reduces the internal magnetic field and in turn its MCE. The total heat exchange estimated by an element-wise sum of heat contributions is 52 J.

Another conventional refrigerant layout consists in packed spheres. Keeping the same useful volume and dimensions of the previous

Fig. 3. Temperature change for 8 evenly spaced Gd sheets, using MFT for the data inputs and an applied magnetic field of 1.0 T perpendicular to the long axis and along the face of the Gd sheets, showing an effective ΔT of 4 K.

example, a set of 221 spheres in a face centered cubic layout is presented (see Fig. 4), whose internal magnetic field is simulated for a vertical uniform external magnetic field of 1.0 T, at 293 K. This simulation contains more than 100 thousand elements in the refrigerant. For the packed spheres layout (4.62 mm diameter spheres), the effective, maximum and minimum ΔT is of 3.50 K, 4.08 K and 3.12 K respectively, generating 71.86 J of heat.

A third refrigerant model was also considered. A set of 5 packed cylinders, each cylinder with the same diameter as the packed spheres (4.62 mm). Each cylinder spans the length of the entire useful volume (100 mm) and the mesh also contains more than 100 thousand total elements. The 5 packed cylinders exhibit an effective, maximum and minimum ΔT of 3.40 K, 4.05 K and 2.87 K and generate 87.00 J of heat (see Fig. 5).

5. Demagnetizing field induced MCE

An emerging alternative method of inducing the MCE is by harnessing the refrigerant’s shape anisotropy (Almeida et al., 2024). Through the orientation dependent demagnetizing field, the rotation of a refrigerant with asymmetric dimensions will induce a change in its internal magnetic field and hence a MCE.

FEMCE provides the option of simulating this demagnetizing field induced MCE, with the same freedom of inputs as for the conventional MCE simulation. Considering the stack of rectangular sheets, the applied field is kept perpendicular to the refrigerant’s long axis and the sheets are rotated by 90°. The change in demagnetizing field generates the heterogeneous ΔT shown on Fig. 6, with an effective ΔT of 1.0 K and a total heat exchange of 13.5 J.

Fig. 4. Internal magnetic field for 221 spheres in a face centered cubic layout, under a vertical, uniform external magnetic of 1.0 T.

Fig. 5. Internal magnetic field for 5 cylinders of 4.62 mm in diameter, under a vertical, uniform external magnetic of 1.0 T.

Fig. 6. Temperature change for 8 evenly spaced Gd sheets, using MFT for the data inputs, and the rotation of the sample around its long axis with an applied field of 1.0 T perpendicular to the long axis and along the face of the Gd sheets, showing an effective ΔT of 1.0 K.

5.1. Post-processing capabilities

Further analysis and post-processing of the data is available to the user by exporting FEMCE generated results. As an example, the ΔT profile on the cross section of each Gd sheet of the refrigerant geometry of the previously shown simulation was evaluated, both for the conventional and demagnetizing field induced MCE, as shown in Fig. 7.

As can be seen in Figs. 3 and 7, for the conventional MCE the temperature change is not flat along the length of the refrigerant. There is a higher ΔT close to the extremities, where the internal field is strongest and \vec{H}_d is weakest. Also, the inner sheets show a more predominant ΔT curvature along the vertical axis, while the outer sheet has a flatter ΔT throughout. Nevertheless, the relative ΔT change is low, in the order of 2–3 %.

In the demagnetizing field induced MCE, the ΔT profile (Fig. 7) shows an overall flatter behavior along the length of the refrigerant, decreasing sharply at the extremities. This ~ 30 % drop of ΔT is an expected consequence of the small rotation-induced change of the demagnetizing field close to the refrigerant edges.

6. Conclusions

FEMCE is a computational tool that allows the simulation of the performance of 3D refrigerants of any shape and thermomagnetic properties. Users can import their own designs through .stl files, or simple models can be created via the built in FEMCE model maker. Mesh generation, creating the 3D model, and simulation are performed in the same graphical environment. The magnetization data $M(H, T)$ is the only required input to simulate the internal magnetic field of the refrigerant. Then, to simulate the MCE, users can either input the $\Delta T(H, T)$ or $C_p(H, T)$, where the latter can be simplified as temperature and/or field

Fig. 7. Profile of the ΔT along the cross section of the refrigerant for the conventional (top) and rotating (bottom) MCE.

independent.

FEMCE outputs multiple critical results beyond the element-wise ΔT , such as the total heat exchange, element-wise magnetization, and the demagnetizing factor for the applied field direction. Average values of multiple properties including effective (volume-averaged) magnetization and ΔT , are estimated, which can be useful as quick figures of merit. Additionally, users can export all simulated results to do their own post processing. FEMCE is a powerful and flexible simulation tool while being user friendly.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

R. Kiefe: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **J.S. Amaral:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

- Almeida, R., Freitas, S.C., Fernandes, C.R., Kiefe, R., Ara'ujo, J.P., Amaral, J.S., Ventura, J.O., Belo, J.H., Silva, D.J., 2024. Rotating magnetocaloric effect in polycrystals—Harnessing the demagnetizing effect. *J. Phys.* 6, 015020.
- Amaral, J.S., Amaral, V., 2010. On estimating the magnetocaloric effect from magnetization measurements. *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 322, 1552 proceedings of the Joint European Magnetic Symposia.
- Badosa, Q., Mañosa, L., Vives, E., Planes, A., Weise, B., Beyer, L., Stern-Taulats, E., 2023. Demagnetizing field induced magnetocaloric effect in Gd. *J. Appl. Phys.* 134, 113902.
- Bahl, C.R.H., Nielsen, K.K., 2009. The effect of demagnetization on the magnetocaloric properties of gadolinium. *J. Appl. Phys.* 105, 013916. https://pubs.aip.org/aip/jap/article-pdf/doi/10.1063/1.3056220/13955810/013916_1_online.pdf.
- Bouchard, J., Nesreddine, H., Galanis, N., 2009. Model of a porous regenerator used for magnetic refrigeration at room temperature. *Int. J. Heat. Mass Transf.* 52, 1223.
- Bruckner, F., Vogler, C., Feischl, M., Praetorius, D., Bergmair, B., Huber, T., Fuger, M., Suess, D., 2012. 3d fem–bem-coupling method to solve magnetostatic Maxwell equations. *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 324, 1862.
- R. Chantrell, J. Fidler, T. Schrefl, and M. Wongsam, *Micromagnetics: finite element approach*, in *Encyclopedia of Materials: Science and Technology*, edited by K. J. Buschow, R. W. Cahn, M. C. Flemings, B. Ilshner, E. J. Kramer, S. Mahajan, and P. Veyssi'ere (Elsevier, Oxford, 2001) pp. 5651–5660.
- Chen, Q., Konrad, A., 1997. A review of finite element open boundary techniques for static and quasi-static electro-magnetic field problems. *IEEE Transac. Magnet.* 33, 663.
- Z. Chen, *Finite element methods and their applications* (2005).
- Christensen, D.V., Bjørk, R., Nielsen, K.K., Bahl, C.R.H., Smith, A., Clausen, S., 2010. Spatially resolved measurements of the magnetocaloric effect and the local magnetic field using thermography. *J. Appl. Phys.* 108, 063913. https://pubs.aip.org/aip/jap/article-pdf/doi/10.1063/1.3487943/13215505/063913_1_online.pdf.
- Coe, J.M.D., 2010. *Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*. Cambridge University Press.
- Franco, V., Blázquez, J., Ipus, J., Law, J., MorenoRamírez, L., Conde, A., 2018. Magnetocaloric effect: from materials research to refrigeration devices. *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 93, 112.
- Gschneidner Jr., K.A., Pecharsky, V.K., 2008. Thirty years of near room temperature magnetic cooling: where we are today and future prospects. *Int. J. Refrig.* - *Revue Internationale du Froid* 31, 945.
- K. Klínar, J.Y. Law, V. Franco, X. Moya, and A. Kitanovski, *Perspectives and energy applications of magnetocaloric, pyromagnetic, electrocaloric, and pyroelectric materials*, *Adv. Energy Mater.* n/a, 2401739.
- M. Kuczmann and A. Iványi, *The finite element method in magnetics* (2008).
- Larson, M.G., Bengzon, F., 2015. *The Finite Element Method: Theory, Implementation, and Applications*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Lipso, K., Nielsen, K., Christensen, D., Bahl, C., Engelbrecht, K., Kuhn, L.Theil, Smith, A., 2011. Measuring the effect of demagnetization in stacks of gadolinium plates using the magnetocaloric effect. *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 323, 3027.
- Mugica, I., Poncet, S., Bouchard, J., 2018. An open source dns solver for the simulation of active magnetocaloric regenerative cycles. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 141, 600.
- Pereira, M.J., Santos, T., Correia, R., Amaral, J.S., Amaral, V.S., Fabbri, S., Albertini, F., 2023. Mapping the magnetocaloric effect at the microscale on a ferromagnetic shape memory alloy with infrared thermography. *JPhys. Mater.* <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7639/acc13b>.
- Plait, A., Giurgea, S., de Laroche Lambert, T., Nika, P., Espanet, C., 2018. Low computational cost semi-analytical magnetostatic model for magnetocaloric refrigeration systems. *AIP. Adv.* 8, 095204. https://pubs.aip.org/aip/adv/article-pdf/doi/10.1063/1.5047654/12856106/095204_1_online.pdf.
- J. Reddy, *An introduction to nonlinear finite element analysis* (2005).
- Smith, A., Bahl, C.R., Bjørk, R., Engelbrecht, K., Nielsen, K.K., Pryds, N., 2012. Materials challenges for high performance magnetocaloric refrigeration devices. *Adv. Energy Mater.* 2, 1288.
- Yu, B., Liu, M., Egolf, P.W., Kitanovski, A., 2010. A review of magnetic refrigerator and heat pump prototypes built before the year 2010. *Int. J. Refrig.* 33, 1029.